

Electrochemical Reversibility of Graphite Oxide

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Crystalline graphite was potentiodynamically charged in 18 M H₂SO₄, 11.6 M HClO₄ and 73 wt% HF. Well-defined over-oxidation peaks could be identified with a charge stoichiometry of 8, 6 and 4 C-atoms per positive charge. Our results are interpreted in terms of a polar structure C_x⁺A⁻ rather than a graphite oxide C_x-OH. From a linear U_{peak}/log γ relationship (γ=1/x), a stoichiometric number ν=9 (for H₂SO₄) is derived for intercalated water molecules. Reversibility of the electrochemical process is poor, however, and it decreases in the order HClO₄>H₂SO₄>HF.

GRAPHITE carbon can be oxidised to yield 'oxides' of very different nature. The products of combustion with O₂ are the small molecules CO₂ and CO. Typical products with chemical oxidants like H₂O₂, H₂SO₄, Ce(NO₃)₄, NaClO, KMnO₄ and many others are, besides CO₂ and CO, aromatic carboxylic acids like mellitic acid C₆(COOH)₆ or pyromellitic acid. A third category finally yields a macromolecule as graphite itself, named graphite oxide. In this case, the reaction conditions are relatively specialised and most promising are H₂SO₄ and/or HNO₃ with a low level of water concentration and the addition of KClO₃, initially found by Brodie^{1,2}. The various chemical methods of preparation were critically reviewed by Boehm and Scholz³. X-Ray structural analysis reveals a layered lattice in analogy to the parent graphite^{4,5}. The distance of planes is 630 pm at 4 wt% incorporated water and increases linearly with this parameter, attaining 900 pm at 40 wt% swelling water⁶. The chemical yield with respect to the graphite is as high as 98%⁴. Elemental analysis gives C/O-ratios 2.5–2.9, correlating arbitrarily with [C₂O₂(OH)₂-H₂O] = C₂O₂ (C/O=2.67)^{7,8} and 1.86–2.29, which leads arbitrarily to [C₂(OH)₂-H₂O] = C₂O (C/O=2.0)⁹.

Graphite intercalation compounds (GIC) are believed to play the role of a precursor for the graphite oxide^{9,10}. Its preparation, originating back to 1840¹¹, was for a long time a domain of preparative inorganic chemistry. However, since the fundamental work of Rüdorff and Hofmann about hundred years later¹², the electrochemical nature of the reversible redox process is appreciated, and electrochemical methods for the preparation and characterisation of the group of salt type GIC's began to prevail. The overall process can be written as

Anions A⁻ are reversibly inserted into the graphite lattice with the degree of intercalation γ, together

with two solvate acid molecules HA and ν water molecules; x is the 'degree of polymerisation' for the carbon. According to Fig. 1, the stoichiometry in the plane corresponds to C_{2.4}⁺·A⁻·2 HA, while the occupation of the interlayer is controlled by the 'stage number'. The reversibility of process (1) was

Fig. 1. In-plane order of anions A⁻ (⊖) and the solvate acid molecules HA (⊕) in every carbon plane in the graphite lattice with the stoichiometric composition C_{2.4}⁺·A⁻·2HA.

proved by galvanostatic^{10,13,14} and potentiodynamic¹⁵ methods. Two reviews on the electrochemistry of GIC's were recently published^{16,17}.

With regard to graphite oxide itself, the electrochemical method was not frequently employed. Initial work on 'anodic over-oxidation of graphite' in concentrated H₂SO₄ displays the typical chemical⁸ and structural⁹ properties of the electro-synthesised graphite oxide. The cathodic rereduction is possible, but with large overvoltages¹⁹, in contrast to the GIC's. As already mentioned, the key intermediate in the course of the chemical or anodic preparation of the graphite oxide is the first

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Fig. 2. Schematic representation (in-plane order) in the original state: C(I) p-quinoid, C(II) o,p-quinoid, and C(III) o-quinoid. In addition the sp^3 -configurations of the carbon planes for partially oxidised graphene-planes are shown for $C_{2.4}^+A^-$, $C_{1.2}^+A^-$, $C_{0.8}^+A^-$, $C_{0.4}^+A^-$, $C_{0.2}^+A^-$ and C^+A^- . The counter ions are not shown.

stage of the corresponding GIC, which may be 'hydrolysed'^{9,10},

Further oxidation steps via the steps $C_{1.2} - OH$, $C_0 - OH$, $C_0 - OH$, $C_4 - OH$ and $C_2 - OH$ may finally lead to graphite oxide $C - OH = C_2O$, corresponding to a degree of oxidation $y = 100\%$. The first step (stage 1 of GIC) has $y = 4.17\%$. Fig. 2 schematically demonstrates the in-plane order of the intermediates, written as the polyradical ion. Usually, covalently bound OH groups or epoxide-etherbonds are postulated^{7,8}. However, the latter have never been identified in the ir spectrum. Alternatively of this sp^3 -configuration of the carbon, a planar layer structure of graphite was proposed²⁰.

A quinoid structure $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \text{CH} - \text{C}(\text{OH}) \\ \diagdown \end{array}$ is not in accordance with the total absence of C-H bond in the ir spectra⁶. Keto groups can be identified with various methods. With regard to oxidation kinetics, the stepwise mechanism was reported^{21,22} in agreement with equation (2).

The question arises, if some of these intermediate stages could be reversibly rereduced. This would be very interesting for an application as active masses in rechargeable batteries. The application of GIC's already proposed by Rüdorff and

Hofmann¹² and more recently thoroughly developed²³⁻²⁶, could be extended to highly interesting theoretical capacities (Table 1). In the following, we like to report on our results.

Experimental

96% H_2SO_4 and 70% $HClO_4$ (both Merck, A.R.) and 73% HF (Fluka, 'reinst') were used.

The prismatic crystalline graphite samples had a mass of about 30 mg and an area of about 0.5 cm^2 (dimensions about $5 \times 5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}$). The samples were wrapped into fine Pt mesh to make up the working electrode. CPP is a natural graphite composite with 20 wt% polypropylene²⁰. HOPG was kindly provided by UCC. Electrochemical measurements were performed in the common three-electrode arrangement. In the case of HF, the cell material was polypropylene. The reference electrode used throughout was $Hg/Hg_2SO_4/1M H_2SO_4$. This electrode is 674 mV positive vs SHE; potentials measured vs this electrode are termed U_s . The design of the Luggin capillary for the measurements in 73% HF is described elsewhere²⁰.

Slow cyclic voltammetric measurements were controlled by a Wenking LT-78 potentiostat and a Wenking VSG 72 voltage scan generator. The current voltage curves were recorded with a Rikadenki RW-21 T XY-recorder.

In preparing the graphite samples after anodic oxidation for the determination of mass and

elemental composition, they were thoroughly rinsed with 70% H_3PO_4 and then with dioxane. Drying was performed over P_2O_5 at 10^{-5} bar at 20° .

Results and Discussion

18 M H_2SO_4 as an electrolyte : Fig. 3 shows the first two cyclic voltammograms in the potential region, where only GIC can be reversibly generated and rereduced. The measurement starts at -0.2 V.

Fig. 3. Slow cyclic current-voltage curves for natural graphite 'GPP', $A=0.5$ cm², in 18 M H_2SO_4 , voltage scan rate = 0.1 mV/s, potential range = $-0.2 \dots +1.2$ V, $m_{CPP}=32.3$ mg: (—) 1st cycle and (---) 2nd cycle.

Beginning with the second cycle, relatively sharp redox peaks can be recognised, corresponding to the 'steps' of the galvanostatic charging curve^{10,13,14}. The total charge of the negative peaks adds up to the charge of the most positive peak, after which the electrode attained the first stage. The follow-up cycles are identical to the second one. Only the first cycle is irregular due to a necessary initial conditioning process. The same effect is observed with pure graphite crystals, it has, therefore, nothing to do with the composite material.

The voltage scan rate is so small that steady state can be assumed at every point. The time constant for the transport of the counterions is

$$\tau = \frac{d^2}{4D} \quad (3)$$

where $d \sim 0.2$ cm and $D = 10^{-6}$ cm² s⁻¹. From this, $\tau \sim 10^8$ s, while the time constant for one peak is $\tau = \Delta U / V_s = 2 \cdot 10^8$ s. An interesting feature is the relatively high 'capacitive current' between the peaks. It is in the order of 1 mA cm⁻², and from

$$j = C_A v_s \quad (4)$$

(C_A = area specific capacity), one obtains $C_A \sim 10$ F/cm². This very high value is due to the fact that the usual figure for the double layer capacity at a metal electrode, $C_A = 20 \mu\text{F/cm}^2$, is multiplied in the case of our lamellar compound by a factor $0.03 \cdot 10^7 / 0.7$ (graphite plane distances = 0.7 nm), and this leads to the value mentioned above.

If the positive potential of scan reversal is extended to +1.8 V, a new very large peak of over-oxidation can be seen at 1.4 V (Fig. 4). The overall composition is now $C_8^+ A^-$ or $C_8 - OH$, and this can be rationalised in terms of a further oxida-

Fig. 4. Slow cyclic current-voltage curves for natural graphite 'GPP', $A=0.5$ cm², in 18 M H_2SO_4 , voltage scan rate = 0.1 mV/s, potential range = $-0.0 \dots +1.8$ V, $m_{CPP}=33.6$ mg: (—) 1st cycle and (---) 2nd cycle.

tion of the graphite lattice, where protons from the solvate acid are leaving the solid^{8g},

Unfortunately, the rereduction is only possible at large overvoltages, and cyclic behaviour is poor.

Nevertheless, the reduction of the solid can be better understood with the polar structure in equation (5) than with a structure with covalent

bonds $\begin{array}{c} \diagdown \\ \text{C}-\text{OH} \\ \diagup \end{array}$, usually discussed in this connection.

A further charge is limited by oxygen evolution at the Pt. Similar maximum composition 'C_{1.0}OH' could be reached with Pt-contacted HOPG¹⁶, while a piece of 'Grafoil' allowed a galvanostatic charge up to C_{3.5}OH¹⁹. We were able to charge a fixed bed of natural graphite flakes up to C_{1.5}OH in 12 M H₂SO₄²⁰. The first reduction proceeded with 70% current efficiency. These examples clearly show that the degree of maximum charge of graphite depends on the experimental conditions and it can nearly reach the composition of chemically prepared samples. The occurrence of a pronounced C₆A-peak or step was never observed before. We systematically varied the positive potential of scan reversal U^r. Up to 1.0 V, current efficiency α of cycling,

$$\alpha = Q_{\text{discharge}}/Q_{\text{charge}} \quad (6)$$

remains high and even becomes quantitative in the second and third cycle (Fig. 5) due to a formation effect. However, U^r becomes more positive, α is lessened more and more and in the third cycle a

Fig. 5. Current efficiency α for the cyclovoltammetric curves at 'OPP', in 18 M H₂SO₄, voltage scan rate=0.1 mV/s in dependence on the potential of scan reversal: (□) 1st cycle, (○) 2nd cycle and (Δ) 3rd cycle.

dramatic decay of α occurs. It is generally believed that this behaviour is coupled with a degradation of the graphite lattice. Nothing is known about the structure of the new material. Fig. 5 shows that this non-steady behaviour occurs in the whole range of over-oxidation.

If the positive endpotential is maintained constant at 1.6 V, the decay of α in the first few cycles is shown in Fig. 6. It is very interesting that it is practically independent of the origin of the crystalline graphite. We could not confirm the constant cyclability of Grafoil, reported by other authors¹⁹. However, HOPG showed an appreciably flatter decrease of α with the cycle number.

Fig. 6. Continuous decrease of current efficiency α with the cycle number in the course of potentiodynamic cycling of 'OPP', various kinds of natural graphite and one HOPG in 18 M H₂SO₄; v_s=0.1 mV/s, range of potentials = -0.2 ... +1.6 V: (□) NG, Ceylon, (Δ) NG, Kropfmühl, (■) NG, Nanshu, (○) NG, Madagaskar, (●) Grafoil, (○) GPP, and (x) HOPG, USA.

11.6 M HClO₄ as an electrolyte : While graphite can be reversibly cycled in the potential range up to C_{2.4} A (1st stage), again cycling becomes irreversible in the over-oxidation zone. Fig. 7 shows again the occurrence of a very pronounced over-oxidation peak, roughly corresponding to C₆ A in this case. Rereduction occurs at extreme overpotentials. It lessens in the second cycle. The current efficiency remains relatively high.

73 wt% HF as an electrolyte : The potentiodynamic cycling in the reversible potential region is

characterised by a very sharp, highly reversible peak at about 1.3 V (Fig. 8). This is more positive than for the other electrolytes. Similar results were

Fig. 7. Slow cyclic current-voltage curves for natural graphite 'OPP', $A=0.5 \text{ cm}^2$ in 11.6 M HClO_4 , voltage scan rate $=0.1 \text{ mV/s}$, potential range $=-0.2 \dots +1.2 \text{ V}$: (—) 1st cycle and (---) 2nd cycle.

Fig. 8. Slow cyclic current-voltage curves for natural graphite, $A=0.5 \text{ cm}^2$, in $78\% \text{ H}_2\text{F}_2$, voltage scan rate $=0.1 \text{ mV/s}$, potential range $=-0.2 \dots +1.3 \text{ V}$; 1st cycle.

previously reported for 73 and 80 wt% HF^{29} . For 50 wt% HF , this sharp double peak could not be observed. If voltage scan is extended to more positive potentials, again a large over-oxidation peak is developed and the total charge corresponds this time to $C_4 A$ (Fig. 9). The last reversible peak is very close to this over-oxidation process. Nevertheless, it is nearly totally irreversible. Consequently, the second cycle displays a rather distorted voltammogram, without any cathodic reduction in the back scan.

Analytical results: We found that the mass of graphite samples, anodically oxidised in $18 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ under potentiodynamic conditions in the whole potential range, is continuously increasing (Fig. 10). The samples were handled as described in Experimental section before weighing back. From this we conclude that a transformation $C_2^+ \text{HSO}_4^- \rightarrow C_2^+ - \text{OH}$ (equation (2)) does not occur, for this would result in a loss of mass. The absolute masses are compatible with $C_2^+ \text{HSO}_4^-$ without the solvate acid, which seems to be removed by the washing

procedure¹². The water and dioxane disappear in the drying process. Correspondingly, the S-concentration in the samples, determined via elemental analysis increases continuously.

Concluding remarks: The objective of our work was the high theoretical capacity, which can be expected for the compositions beyond the first stage. Table 1 compiles some values for graphite fluoride. For graphite oxide, the figures would be even higher.

We found that charging to $C_2^+ \text{HSO}_4^-$ or to $C_2^+ \text{ClO}_4^-$ is possible, but current efficiency for rereduction decreases within a few cycles or is zero from the beginning for the fluoride. This is due to irreversible changes in the graphite host lattice, the nature of which is not yet understood.

Table 2 compiles our results for the three relatively concentrated acids. The highest charge is observed for H_2F_2 , but reversibility is lowest. H_2SO_4 gives a good current efficiency in the first

Fig. 9. Slow cyclic current-voltage curves for natural graphite, $A=0.5 \text{ cm}^2$, in 73% H_3F_3 ; voltage scan rate=0.1 mV/s, potential range=-0.2 ... +1.6 V. The first and the second cycle are shown.

Fig. 10. Mass increase of natural graphite on anodic oxidation in 18 M H_2SO_4 in dependence on the end-potential of the first anodic scan; voltage scan rate=0.1 mV/s.

TABLE 1—THEORETICAL ELECTROCHEMICAL EQUIVALENTS m_e FOR VARIOUS GRAPHITE FLUORIDES

Graphite fluoride	m_e (Ah kg^{-1})
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_4\text{HF}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{F}_2$	66.2
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{HF}_2$	198
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_4\text{HF}_3$	308
CF	865

cycle, but it decreases rapidly in the follow-up cycles (Fig. 6). The peak potentials of the over-oxidation are nearly the same in all three electrolytes.

TABLE 2—OVERVIEW ON ELECTROCHEMICAL RESULTS IN OVER-OXIDATION REGION

	18 M H_2SO_4 C_6	11.6 M HClO_4 , 73 % HF C_6	73 % HF C_4
1. C-Stoichiometry of over-oxidation peak per Faraday			
2. Anodic peakpotential U_s/V (1st cycle)	1.41	1.43	1.43
3. Reduction peak U_s/V	0.84	~0.2	0.65
4. Current efficiency $\alpha/\%$ 1st cycle/2nd cycle	85/60	79/77	→0

If we assume that equilibrium potentials are established in the course of the very slow cyclic voltammograms, Nernst equation can be employed with respect to reaction (1),

$$U = U^0 + \frac{RT}{yF} \ln \frac{[C^{\nu+}] [A^-]^\nu [HA]^{2\nu} [H_2O]^{\nu\nu}}{[C] \cdot (a_A)^y \cdot (a_{HA})^{2\nu} \cdot (a_{H_2O})^{\nu\nu}} \quad (7)$$

The activities in the solid state are given in brackets. Recently, we evaluated the consequences for a systematical change of electrolyte composition⁴⁰. The most important feature was an exponential increase of a_{HA} with increasing molar concentration c of the acid ($a_{HA} = k \exp(A \cdot c)$), finally leading to a linear U/c -relationship, as experimentally observed. In the case of the measurements reported here, the electrolyte composition was kept constant. We assume in a first approximation the activity of the carbon species to be constant, too. Then equation (7) is reduced to

$$U = U^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [A^-] [HA]^2 [H_2O]^\nu \quad (8)$$

A consideration of a constant stoichiometric ratio according to equation (1), $[A^-] : [HA] : [H_2O] = 1 : 2 : \nu$, leads to

$$U = U^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [A^-] [2 A^-]^2 [\nu A^-]^\nu \quad (9)$$

From this, one obtains straightforwardly,

$$U = U^0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln 4\nu^\nu + \frac{(\nu+3)RT}{F} \ln [A^-] \quad (10)$$

$[A^-]$ is transformed into y by

$$[A^-] = B \cdot y \quad (11)$$

Thus, one finally obtains,

$$U = U^0 + 2.30 \frac{(\nu+3)RT}{F} \log y \quad (12)$$

We plotted accordingly the peakpotentials of Figs. 3 and 4 (for the positive going polarisation) vs $\log y$, which is obtained by integration of the total charge involved in the peaks, and indeed, a straight line is obtained (Fig. 11). From the slope of the line ($\sim 700 \text{ mV}$ per decade), $\nu \sim 9$ is derived. Uptil now, nearly nothing is known about ν due to great analytical problems. We derived by this way for the first time via an indirect electrochemical method a stoichiometric number ν . It

Fig 11. Semilogarithmic plot of degree of intercalation y vs the potential of the corresponding oxidation peak, anodic oxidation of natural graphite in 18 M H_2SO_4 : (X) 1st cycle, (O) 2nd cycle and (●) 3rd cycle.

is important to note that the point for the over-oxidation peak lies on the line and this seems to support our view that it means an extension of the polar structural acknowledged hitherto for the reversible potential regime.

The sequence of peaks in the case of 73% HF is within a much narrower potential difference (Figs. 8 and 9). ΔU is about 0.65 V for 73% HF instead of 1.15 V for 18 M H_2SO_4 , and $\nu=2$ follows in this case.

Thus we are able to contribute to the basic understanding of graphite oxide, and we hope that this facilitates to reach our primary goal, an improvement of its electrochemical reversibility.

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